

THE APPLICATION OF SEM TECHNIQUE FOR THE ASSESSMENT OF FACTORS INFLUENCING LOCAL COMMUNITY MEMBERS IN DESTINATION DEVELOPMENT: A STUDY OF THE DISTRICT OF JAMMU AND KASHMIR – INDIA

Zaffar Iqbal*

Abstract

Community participation is a tool to achieve sustainable tourism development. The purpose of this paper is to identify the factors influencing community participation in destination building and its consequences for the local inhabitants in the form of social, tourism and economic development. The model is based upon the various constructs portraying the influence of various factors on community participation. This study used explorative factor analysis, confirmatory factor analysis and Structural Equation Modeling [SEM] technique for determining the structural estimates between constructs. Data for this study was collected from 214 questionnaires from residents of different tourist destinations in Poonch district of Jammu and Kashmir [J&K]. The result revealed that personal, economic factor has the most significant impact followed by social and least by environmental factor upon the local community participation. Moreover, the respondents agreed that destination development has contributed a lot in terms of economic and followed by other two factors. Conclusions endorse the view of the way how local community perceive tourism plays an important role in the development of indigenous tourism.

Key words: Community participation. Destination development. Economic development. Tourism development.

A APLICAÇÃO DO SEM PARA A AVALIAÇÃO DE FATORES QUE INFLUEM EM MEMBROS DA COMUNIDADE LOCAL NO DESENVOLVIMENTO DO DESTINO: UM ESTUDO DO DISTRITO DE JAMMU E KASHMIR – ÍNDIA**Resumo**

A participação comunitária é uma ferramenta para alcançar o desenvolvimento turístico sustentável. O objetivo deste documento é identificar os fatores que influenciam a participação da comunidade na construção de destinos e as consequências para os habitantes locais na forma de desenvolvimento social, turístico e econômico. O modelo teórico baseia-se nas diversas construções que retratam os fatores de influência na participação comunitária. Este estudo utiliza a análise exploratória fatorial, a análise confirmatória fatorial e a técnica de modelagem de equações estruturais para determinar as estimativas de estruturas entre construções. Os dados para este estudo obtiveram 214 solicitações de residentes de diferentes destinos turísticos no distrito de Poonch de Jammu and Kashmira [J&K]. Os resultados mostram que fatores pessoais e econômicos têm o impacto mais significativo seguido pelo social e menos pelo fator ambiental sobre a participação da comunidade local. Além disso, os respondentes concordaram que o desenvolvimento do destino tem contribuído muito em termos econômicos e seguido por outros dois fatores. As conclusões reforçam a ideia de que o modo pelo qual a comunidade local percebe o turismo tem um papel importante no desenvolvimento turístico autóctone.

Palavras-chave: Participação comunitária. Desenvolvimento de destinos. Desenvolvimento econômico. Desenvolvimento turístico.

LA APLICACIÓN DE SEM PARA LA EVALUACIÓN DE FACTORES QUE INFLUYEN EN MIEMBROS DE LA COMUNIDAD LOCAL EN EL DESARROLLO DEL DESTINO: UN ESTUDIO DEL DISTRITO DE JAMMU Y KASHMIR – INDIA**Resumen**

La participación comunitaria es una herramienta para lograr un desarrollo turístico sostenible. El propósito de este documento es identificar los factores que influyen en la participación de la comunidad en la construcción de destinos y sus consecuencias para los habitantes locales en forma de desarrollo social, turístico y económico. El modelo se basa en las diversas construcciones que retratan la influencia de varios factores en la participación comunitaria. Este estudio analizó el análisis factorial exploratorio, el análisis factorial confirmatorio y la técnica de modelado de ecuaciones estructurales para determinar las estructuras estructurales entre construcciones. Los datos para este estudio se obtuvieron de 214 cuestionarios de residentes de diferentes destinos turísticos en el distrito de Poonch de Jammu and Kashmira [J&K]. Los resultados muestran que el factor económico y el personal tiene el impacto más significativo seguido del factor social y el menos ambiental en la participación de la comunidad local. Además, los encuestados coincidieron en que el desarrollo del destino ha contribuido mucho en términos económicos y seguido de otros dos factores. Las conclusiones refuerzan la idea de que el modo como la comunidad local percibe el turismo juega un papel importante en el desarrollo del turismo indígena.

Palabras clave: Participación comunitaria. Desarrollo de destinos. Desarrollo económico. Desarrollo turístico.

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* M Phil in Commerce (2019), Master in Commerce/M Com (2017), Bachelor in Commerce/ B Com (2015). Currently pursuing PhD in the department of commerce university of Jammu. [zaffariqbal000@gmail.com]

1 INTRODUCTION

In many developing countries tourism industry has evolved overtime and the role it played in socio-economic development of many countries is widely understood and well established.

The importance of community participation in tourism development has been agreed by most researchers. Khoshnam et al. (2015) argued that community participation can specify the appropriate local development and its stages and select the suitable procedures in order to achieve the desired development.

Tasci et al 2014 opined that the goal of any projects can't be fully achieved unless people meaningfully participate in it. Khani (2012) suggested that participation is instrumental to achieve sustainability for tourism and community development.

In the context of destination development, Pin Yu et al (2018), point out that the environment and natural resources would not be much exploited with the involvement of local residents because the local community is more aware on the extent to which the tourism and environment should be developed.

Muganda et al (2013) added that local people participation in tourism development contribute positively to the health of tourism industry and successful community development. Mak et al (2017) added that community participation is a process to achieve sustainable tourism development. One of the beneficial impacts of community participation in tourism development is the change in socio-economic development of local residents (Liu et al., 2015).

For example, in the context of Poonch district, before the participation of local community in tourism development, most of the local inhabitants were involved as a manual labour or in agriculture sector. However, with the establishment of tourism industry, their living standards have improved and they have shifted to better economic sector. Further community participation in tourism development is a tool to achieve sustainability in tourism sector Sharma & Dyer (2009).

Pin Yu et al (2018) suggest that participation is instrumental to achieve sustainability for tourism and community development. Community participation in destination development has emerged as the sensible option to achieve sustainability. It has been argued that successful tourist destination is totally dependent upon the cooperation and willingness of host community. This is also supported by the World Tourism Organisation (WTO), World Travel and Tourism Council (WTTC), The Earth Council, Manila Declaration 1980, and Osaka Tourism Forum.

There are end number of researcher studies which clearly shows that the development of tourism industry should not be considered only from the economic perspective only, but more importantly it should be developed in a sustainable manner with the involvement of local community members (Latip et al., 2017).

Tourism development acts as a catalyst for the sustainability and community development. Tourism development has important role on improving standard of local community members (Safar et al., 2015). Tourism industry helps to remove people from the clutches of poverty, traditional economic activities and from being marginalize (Magigi & Ramadhan, 2013).

On the bases of above mention facts, community participation must be encouraged. Being located on indo-Pak border with rugged topography it's not easy to establish and run any kind of industry except tourism industry.

Despite the fact that Poonch district is bestowed with immense tourism potential and that is not yet explored and developed. Mostly people are engage in manual labour and agriculture farming for their livelihood. Consequently, tourism industry has the potential to increase their income and improve their living standard.

Conversely, the local inhabitants will be adversely affected through development of tourism industry by the outside parties. In order to mitigate this effect and achieve sustainability in tourism sector it becomes necessary to involve the local community for future tourism development.

Therefore how local community perceive tourism plays an important role in the development of indigenous tourism. Hence, this study attempted to investigate the factors influencing community participation and the benefits accrued by the local inhabitants. By knowing these factors, relevant policy could be framed to enhance community participation in destination building in Poonch district or in any other destinations.

The process of destination development through local inhabitants is an important tool for community development also. Hence many local communities have started devoting their time towards tourism development in order to provide economic, social-cultural and overall development of the community.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESIS DEVELOPMENT

Local tourism success lies upon the perception and attitude of host community (Zhu et al., 2016). Social exchange theory delineates that resident's perception and attitude for future tourism development

largely depends upon the tourism impacts (Afthanorhan et al., 2017).

However, it is argued that during the course of tourism development activities some people benefit while others are negatively affected and host community support in tourism industry is considered as a tool to achieve sustainability. Further, positive benefits incurring from tourism development significantly influence the perception of local inhabitants and vice-versa (Hanafiah et al., 2013).

Mrema (2015) has pointed out that tourism has a significant contribution towards poverty alleviation among local communities. But at the same time it has been argued that the goal of any project can't be fully achieved unless people meaningfully participate in it (Tesda et al., 2016). Mak et al. (2017) added that community participation is a process to achieve sustainable tourism development. This participation is instrumental to achieve sustainability for tourism and community development (Pin Yu et al., 2018).

Hussein (2017) has argued that economic and socio cultural benefits positively influence host community attitude (Pin Yu et al., 2018) and act as a catalyst for the community welfare especially when local people have control of the tourism resources in their area (Provia et al., 2017). Peters et al. (2018) study delineate that economic impacts followed by socio-cultural are the major factor influencing local residents participation in tourism development. Further, Jamwal (2014) argued that it increases pride about local culture and it has encouraged variety of cultural activities for the host community.

Income and family encouragement act as a significant influencer for future tourism development (Salleh et al., 2016). Huong & lee (2017) argued that social and environmental impacts from tourism are major factors in influencing local residents' attitude towards tourism related activities. Rasoolimanesh *et al* (2017) advocated that tourism development through community participation has brought household incomes, improvement in standards of living and employment opportunities for local community.

Meimand et al (2017) destination development has created social and cultural benefits for the host community. Local resident's perceptions of social and environmental impacts from tourism act as a significant influencer on their attitude (Huong & lee, 2017). For successful tourism development it should be planned and managed in a sustainable manner and key to achieve sustainability is the stakeholders (host community, tourism entrepreneurs and community leaders).

The engagement of all stakeholders is crucial to ensuring the sustainability of development of tourism. (Limpho, 2015). Decentralization and community

involvement in decision making have been accepted as a tool to mitigate negative impact of tourism across the globe.

Likewise, several studies found that perceived personal economic benefit from tourism is the most influential constructs explaining support for tourism development while personal economic benefits acclaimed as a stronger factor of residents attitude of tourism and their support.

A number of theories have been incorporated to identify the factors influencing community participation in destination development and SET seems to be the most dominant among all the theories. This states that perception of local community members will be directly affected by the benefits derived from tourism development. If they believe that if the benefits outweigh the associated costs then they may be encouraged to support future tourism development.

Under this study four factors have been identified as the antecedents of community participation which are social factor, economic factor, personal factor and environmental factor.

The use of *economic factor* to explain the community participation in tourism development has been common among various social-science researchers. (Andriotis & Vaughan 2003) has argued in its study that tourism's beneficial impacts on the economy of their region, on employment, on government revenues and especially on local community has enhanced the community participation in tourism development.

Tourism development through community participation provides opportunities to the local inhabitants to sell their local crafts to the tourist (provia et al., 2017). Inhabitants strongly admitted that tourism development has boosted their living standard by creating more job opportunity and infrastructure development (provia et al., 2017) tourism development through community participation provides a lot of important opportunity for personal economic benefits especially during a time of crisis.

Thus, various research studies have found a significant relationship between resident's personal economic benefits of tourism and their attitude toward tourism development. Within the tourism literature some studies conclude that residents who benefits economically from tourism tend to hold a more favorable attitude of the impact than those who receive lesser or no benefits (e.g. Hanafiah et al 2013; Khoshnam et al 2015; Şahin & Akova, (2019).

Therefore, the second most important factors which plays a major role in persuasion of local community attitude is *social factor* because nowadays people are more concerned about their social belonging. The social and environmental impacts from

tourism significantly affect attitudes of local community for tourism development. Residents will support tourism activities in the community when positive social and environmental impacts are perceived (Huong and Lee, 2017).

Although Jurowski et al. (1997) study delineates that resident' attitudes toward tourism development and social impacts share a significantly positive relation each influencing the other overall favorably. Although Jurowski et al. (1997) has also found "Perceived Social Impact" is an important factor concerning support for tourism development (Bertan, 2019).

Combining the results of Pham and Kayat (2011), it can be seen that social and *environmental impacts* from tourism is an important issue for examination in studies of tourism development through community participation (Hanafiah et al, 2013). The majority of the respondents admitted that tourism provides community participation helps to create more recreational activities and it is the foremost reason of entertainment for the local inhabitants. (Hanafiah et al 2013).

The perceived socio-cultural cost had a negative influence on the perception of community participation toward the support for tourism development. Mostly the respondents are more inclined toward the positivity of the tourism development as most of them admitted that tourism provides them social and cultural benefits. (Afthanorhanet al., 2017).

It has been found that tourism development yield more negative impact on natural resources, created significant solid and air waste and caused destruction of the natural landscape. (Safari et al., 2015).

From a positive environmental perspective, the respondents agreed that tourism development improves community appearance and helps increase restoration of buildings and natural resources.

Community participation empowers its members to mobilize their capabilities in managing resources, enables them to make decisions, and exert control over activities that directly affect their lives (Jaafar et al., 2015). Huong & Lee (2017) has found social and environmental impacts from tourism significantly affect attitudes of local community members for tourism development (Aref et al 2010).

Local communities have crucial role in providing a good environmental condition for tourists. The community felt that tourism can help improve the local environment which included items such as preservation of natural and cultural resources, and beauty of the island (Munhurrin & Naidoo, 2011).

Safari et al., (2015) opined that host community involvement is critical for sustainable management of resources and the overall tourism development.

Residents' personal economic benefits from tourism emerged to be a significant predictor of their pro-tourism development behavior (Ribeiro et al., 2017).

Studies found that the residents who drew personal benefits from tourism activities were more likely to support tourism development (Peters et al., 2018). (Mugizi et al., 2017) personal Income derived from tourism activities had a significant influence on host community member attitude for future tourism development. (Latip et al., 2017).

The sustainability of tourism destination largely depends upon *personal perceptions* of local community members. An individual with experience on tourism perceive greater benefits from tourism in terms of generation of additional family income than individual without such experience (Salleh et al., 2016). Knowledgeable people exhibits positive relationship with perceived benefits of tourism in community life, personal life and economy as whole (Andereck et al., 2005 & Meimand et al., 2017).

Several studies have investigated how local community members perceive tourism development is impacting their community life. Under this study tourism repercussions are investigated under three heads which are economic development, social development and tourism development.

Social development always start with the integration of local people unless and until local people will not join hands with each other there is no way that anything could be achieved weather that is social development, tourism development, economic development these things would be easily achieved only when there would be involvement of local people in formulation of policies and programme related to all these sectors.

Tourism development has produced a lot of positive benefits for the local community in the form of cross-cultural exchange and understanding of old age traditional culture (Zhu et al., 2017) respondents admitted that tourism development has provided an opportunity to the local community members for traditional cultural exchanges (Zhu et al., 2017) study delineate that local residents perceived tourism as a development that provides cultural identity and activity, cultural exchange, and valuable meeting experiences with tourists..

The host community believed that social and cultural life in the Northern coast has improved resulting as cultural exchange between tourists and residents, creating positive impacts on the cultural activities of the community, providing more recreational and sport areas for local residents, and maintaining high standards of roads and public facilities (Munhurrin & Naidoo 2011) the benefits

included supporting schools, health facilities, and supply of potable water (Safari et al 2015).

Almost all the respondents praised tourism because it provides incentives for the restoration of historical building. (Andriotis & Vaughan 2003). Liu & var 1986 in his study inhabitants had admitted that community based tourism had given opportunities for cultural exchange and better understanding of world culture.

Economic development is the transformation of low income economy to higher income economy and enhancing the living standard of people of whole nation. Tourism development acts as a catalyst for the national economy (Mike et al., 2018). Respondents have admitted that tourism development have attracted more investment and spending in their region. Residents admitted that tourism created more jobs, attracted more investment in their community, and generated economic benefits to local people and businesses (Yoon et al., 2001).

Hanafiah et al. (2013) study delineate that tourism development creates a lot of job opportunities for the local people and it improves the economic as well as the living standard of people, (Mastura.et.al 2015) locals felt that tourism development provided unparalleled opportunities for them to enter new economic sectors. (Andriotis & Vaughan (2003) have found that tourism development is the economic asset for the welfare of community member and it had attracted more investment in their region.

Tourism development in their community has resulted into more jobs, attracting more investment to the community, providing more business for local people, creating additional tax revenue (Munhurrun & Naidoo, 2011).

Safari et al. (2015), study show that tourism has an important role in improving standard of living of community members and enhancing small business. Mugizi et al. (2017) has argued that revenue from tourism sector has enhanced the foreign reserves. (Afthanorhan et al., 2017) Has pointed out that tourism development in their area has improved the area appearance and it also helps in providing incentive for the restoration.

Norlida et al. (2016) argued that community participation leads to sustained tourism development. Faulkner & Tideswell (1997) and Ogechi & Oyinkansola (2012) concluded that community participation leads to improved appearance of the area and housing condition of local inhabitants.

Community participation helps to mitigate the exploitation of natural resources in the development process. Muganda et al. (2013), has argued that tourism development through community participation

helps to maintain natural landscape. Tourism development brings more investments and spending.

Tourism can positively promote a community to potential investors and residents as well as visitors Hasan & Siddiqui (2016). Roads, hospitals and other public facilities have improved Thokchom, (2014). Tourism acts as a catalyst in the development of the backward and far flung areas of particular region Boonsiritomachai & Phonthanukitithaworn, (2019).

Developing of tourism industry is responsible for generating direct as well as indirect employment (rasoolimanesh et al., 2017). It also brings additional source of income and contributes towards improvement in their basic facilities such as water, electricity and road connectivity (Nkemngu, 2012).

Norlida et al. (2016) argued that community participation leads to sustained tourism development. Faulkner & Tideswell (1997) & Ogechi & Oyinkansola (2012) concluded that community participation leads to improved appearance of the area and housing condition of local inhabitants. Many a time some literary work by the local inhabitants acts as the promotional technique for the tourist destination and hence this district has been bestowed with many renowned literary personalities (Sengel et al., 2019).

Based on aforesaid literature review, following hypotheses have been set for the study.

Hyp1: Community participation is influenced by economic factor

Hyp2: Community participation is influenced by social factors

Hyp3: community participation is significantly influenced by personal factor

Hyp4: Community participation is significantly impacted by environmental factors

Hyp5: Community participation significantly contributes toward economic development, social development and tourism development.

3 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Study area

Jammu and Kashmir is the northern most state of India and shares its border with three countries, i.e. Afghanistan, China and Pakistan. It extends from 32°17' N to 37°50' N latitude and from 73°26' E to 80°30' E longitude, covering an area of 2, 22,236 square kilometers with population of 125.41 lakh persons as per 2011 census. Poonch is one of the 22 districts of the state of J&K and also known as mini Kashmir.

It is bounded by a line of control on the north, west and southern sides. Poonch valley is separated from the Kashmir valley by the PirPanjal ranges,

specifically its peer-ki-gali which bifurcate Jammu province from Kashmir province.

Located at 33.77°N 74.1°E, Poonch has an average elevation of 981 metres above sea level. The district has four tehsils namely, Haveli, Mendhar, Surankote and Mandi. The 1947-48 war divided the Poonch district into two parts: one part is controlled by India and other became the part of Pakistan occupied Kashmir (Dar, 2014).

Figure 1: Location of district Poonch, in India.

Source: Mughal et al. (2017 : 369).

3.2 Data collection

A quantitative approach, using a questionnaire, was used to collect data from the residents of Poonch district of J&K. the questionnaire was framed on the bases of various previous community participation studies (Riberio et al. (2017); Meimand et al. (2017); Afthanorhan et al. (2017); Zhu et al. (2017); Garcia et al. (2016); Pin et al. (2018); Rasoolimanesh et al., 2015) was later modified in accordance to the study, thus making the tool more appropriate for community participation in destination development.

Data were collected from the community members who were directly or indirectly engaged in tourism related activities during the month of February and March in 2018, with potential respondents identified using judgmental and convenient sampling technique.

3.3 Data analysis

As this research study has a large number of related items and wishes to explore the underlying structure of this set of items, factor analysis was used in order to reduce the number of items.

Summers are short whereas winters are cool and characterized by rainfall and moderate snowfall at lower places. With the completion of the Mughal Road connecting Buzliaz in Poonch to Shopian in Kashmir, a direct connection between Jammu and Srinagar has been set. As per the 2011 census, the Poonch district has a population of 4,76,826 which exhibits ethnic and linguistic differences from the rest of the state. The largest ethnic group of the area is the Gujjar tribe which makes up 48% of the population in Poonch.

Figure 2: Tourist map of district Poonch.

Source: Poonch district government (2020s/d).

The indicator variables related to factor influencing community participation and their repercussions construct were subjected to an exploratory factor analysis to identify the underlying factors and to test whether the factors extracted are similar to the dimensions proposed in the study Pin et al., (2018).

The Principal Component Extraction method along with Varimax rotation was performed to identify the underlying factors for antecedents and outcomes construct and factor loading of 0.50 or above on the items was taken into consideration.

Thereafter, CFA was incorporated to assess the validity and reliability of the constructs. Second order model have been constructed for social, economic factor influencing cp and their outcomes constructs after EFA. The fit indices of measurement models are found to be in line with the set criteria.

The goodness of fit indices like CFI, GFI, TLI and AGFI all are greater than 0.90 or touching the limit and badness of fit criteria like RMSEA should be less than 0.80 (Khoshnam et al.,2015).

In order to gauge the internal consistency among the items cronbach's alpha was assessed (cronbach, 1951). The assessment of scale reliability was done by examining composite reliability measure and the

average variance extracted (AVE) which is depicted in table. By means of confirmatory factor analysis (CFA), convergent validity was established by the magnitude standardized estimates (> 0.5) and significance of the factor loading i.e. < 0.05 (riberio et al., 2017).

Further, to check the discriminant validity variance extracted was compared with squared correlation of diverse scales as suggested by (Garcia et al., 2016). The outcomes of the assessment are mentioned in table. Further, the proposed conceptual framework, including measurement models and structural model, were assessed through SEM with the help of AMOS 16.0.

SEM is an appropriate technique to be incorporated for estimating and testing a network of relationship between variables (measured variables and latent construct) (Salleh et al., 2016) is a comprehensive statistical approach to testing hypotheses about relations among observed and latent variables (liang& hui, 2016).

SEM also helps a researcher to test a set of regression equations simultaneously. SEM is an effective model testing and improving method that enables theoretical models to be tested as a whole and that can explain the cause and effect relationship of the variables in mixed hypotheses which are related to the models based on statistical dependence (Kocakaya & Kocakaya, 2014).

4 ANALYSIS AND FINDINGS

4.1 Data Presentation

As evident from the table 1, the respondents were classified into seven categories namely gender, age, marital status, family size, qualification, occupation and monthly income of the respondents.

Of 214 respondents, 98.3% are male and 1.6% are female. As female were not much quite active in outside activities due to conservative culture. Age-wise, 13.08% fall in age group-I (below 20 years), 56.54% fall in age group-II (20-30 years), 25.23% fall in age group-III (30-50 years) and rest 5.14% fall in last age group-IV (above 50 years).

According to marital status of the respondents, 57.47% respondents are married and rests 42.52% are unmarried. Monthly income-wise, 8.41% respondents fall in income group-I (below Rs. 15,000), 50.46% respondents fall in income group-II (Rs. 15,000- Rs. 30,000), 29.90% respondents fall in income group III (Rs. 30,000- Rs 40,000) and 10.74% falls in the last income group IV (Rs.40,000 and above).

The respondents falling in four educational sub-groups include 14.95% respondents in group-I (below

primary), 38.31% respondent in group-II (upto matric), 40.65% respondents in group-III (graduation) and 6.07% respondent in group-IV (post-graduation).

Table 1: Profile of Respondents.

S. No	Variables	Subgroup	Freq.	Perc. (%)
1	Gender	Male	219	98.3
		Female	06	1.6
2	Age	Upto 20 yrs	28	13.08
		Between 20-30 yrs	121	56.54
		Between 30-50 yrs	54	25.23
		Above 50 yrs	11	5.14
3	Marital status	Married	123	57.47
		Unmarried	91	42.52
4	Family size	2-4 members	42	19.62
		4-6 members	114	53.27
		6-8 members	48	22.42
		Above 8 members	10	4.67
5	Qualification	Below primary	32	14.95
		Middle-higher secondary	82	38.31
		Graduate	87	40.65
		Post-graduate	13	6.07
6	Occupation	Govt. Job	18	8.41
		Private job	12	5.60
		Business	119	55.60
		Others	65	3.37
7	Monthly income	Below Rs 15000	18	8.41
		Rs 15000- Rs 30000	108	50.46
		Rs 30000- Rs 40000	64	29.90
		Above Rs 40000	23	10.74

Source: proper elaboration.

Further according to family size, 19.62% respondents fall under group- I (2-4 members), 53.27% respondents in group- II (4-6 members), 22.42% respondents fall under group- III (6-8 members) and rest 4.67% falls under group (above 8 members).

Demarcation according to profession, 8.41% respondents fall under group- I (govt.job), 5.60% falls under group- II (private job), 55.60% falls under group-III (business), and rest 30.37% falls under group- IV (other professions) respectively.

The last category is about whether local residents were engaged in tourism related activities or not 99% respondents fall under the category of engagement in tourism related activities.

Figure 1: Proposed Measurement and structural model.

Source: proper elaboration.

Table 2: Fit indices of measurement models.

Dimension/construct	Chi sq/df	GFI	AGFI	RMR	RMSEA	TLI	CFI
Economic construct	1.141	0.96	0.93	0.031	0.028	0.98	0.98
Social construct	1.684	0.96	0.91	0.038	0.062	0.90	0.94
Personal construct	2.328	0.95	0.89	0.049	0.060	0.93	0.96
Environmental construct	1.346	0.98	0.94	0.025	0.044	0.95	0.98
Economic development	1.913	0.97	0.91	0.034	0.072	0.92	0.96
Social development	2.990	0.94	0.87	0.062	0.096	0.70	0.82
Tourism development	1.754	0.92	0.87	0.072	0.084	0.77	0.85

Legend: Goodness-of-Fit statistic (GFI), Comparative Fit Index (CFI), Root Mean square Residual (RMR), Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA), Tucker Lewis index (TLI) and Adjusted Goodness of Fit Index (AGFI).

Source: proper elaboration.

This study includes seven constructs namely, social factor, economic factor, personal factor and environmental factor as antecedents and three more constructs as outcome of destination development for the local inhabitants such as economic development, social development and tourism development. To assess the measurement model it is necessary to check indicators and constructs reliability, as well as convergent and discriminant validity.

In order to assess the indicators reliability, the loading must be above 0.50 of each item to be considered acceptable (Peters et al., 2018). The establishments of measurement model were determined through CFA with the help of AMOS 16.0.

Numerous measures of fit indices were used to evaluate the measurement model quality. The traditional chi-square was used to check the overall model fit, further many more fit indices were utilized to evaluate the overall fit of a CFA solution, such as TLI, GFI, RMR, CFI, AGFI and RMSEA.

Such indices were incorporated in this research due to their overall satisfactory performance in the simulation (Mike et al., 2018). As shown in table the CFA model fit the sample data well for each construct:

i.e. $\chi^2/df=1.141$, $RMR=0.031$, $RMSEA=0.028$, $GFI=0.967$, $AGFI=0.936$, $CFI=0.988$ and $TLI=0.980$.

Thereafter, Structural equation modeling, a multivariate technique was implied to determine various relations; it was incorporated to test the hypothesized relationships in the model. The overall fit measures suggest that the data provide a good fit for the hypothesized casual model (fig 1).

After running SEM significant relationship of antecedents of community participation such as economic, social, personal and environmental factors and destination development outcomes constructs such as social, economic and tourism development was found. The SRW values found for social, economic, personal and environmental factors influencing community participation in destination development were, respectively: 0.910, 0.768, 0.756 and 0.687.

These SRW values indicate that community participation is highly influenced by economic factor followed by personal factor which was followed by social factor which depict that people are more inclined toward economic and personal factor rather than social factor which also possess some importance.

Furthermore, the results show that environmental factor is the least influencing factor for community participation in destination development. However, the SRW values derived for the outcomes received by local community members are as 0.897 for economic development which is considered relatively high and which was followed by social development and tourism development, the SRW values for these two constructs were as 0.743 and 0.656.

4.2 Discussion

The aim of this study was to contribute to the literature by investigating the influence of economic, social, personal and environmental factors on community participation in destination development and outcomes received by the local indigenous community in the form of social, economic and tourism development. We decided to employ social exchange theory, which has been recognized in various pieces of prominent research, in our analysis using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM).

This study is the first research that has been done on Poonch district of Jammu and Kashmir till yet. Remarkably, the entire model framed in this research study has shown positive and significant relation with various dimension and tourism development as well as for the local community.

The results obtained depicts that local inhabitants are inclined towards the tourism sector as such there is no other option available for the livelihood due to the rugged and terrain topography. That means the respondents admitted that tourism development ultimately influences their quality of life whether they regard it positive or not.

The findings of this study indicate that community participation is significantly influenced by social, economic, personal and environmental factor as depicted by their SRW values. The results revealed that the effects of destination development on social, economic and tourism development are significant (H5-H7). Several other studies have revealed significant relation between the antecedents and outcomes of destination development through community participation (Rasoolimanesh et al. (2017), Hussein, (2017), Garcia et al. (2016).

Earlier studies have focused on different factors viz. personal economic benefits, community attachment (Huong & Lee, 2017), motivation, opportunity, awareness and knowledge (Rasoolimanesh et al., 2017), access to information, political will and civic education (Tesda et al., 2015), domicile, gender, acknowledgement and duration of stay (Sawee, 2015), social capital, skill & knowledge, training, external support, access to utilities and

employment (Provia et al., 2017), economic, social and future support (Hanafiah et al., 2013), social demographic characteristic, level of personal involvement, level of education & accountability (Safari et al., 2015).

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Thus, one can conclude that community members are willing to support further destination development due to positive benefits associated with it. Therefore destination development has the possibility of yielding more positive and little negative on the local environment as delineated by the results attained.

Findings provided support for hypothesis 1 and hypothesis 2 that proposed a direct positive relationship between the social and economic factors influencing community participation in destination development. This is due to the fact that destination development has deep and durable economic repercussions for the local community residing around that particular destination and especially for those who are heavily dependent on the tourism industry.

Respondents opined that from the social perspective 'socially more secure (M= 3.60)' and 'reduction in family crises (M= 3.22)'. 'Social pride & involvement' and 'impetus to participatory spirit & belongingness' creates a group of socially active people (M= 4.00), bring social recognition (M= 4.21), promotes cultural exchange & education (M= 4.06).

From the economic perspective respondents admitted that 'increase economic activities in other sectors (M= 3.92)', 'leads to poverty eradication (M= 3.85)' and 'generate revenue for local authority (M= 3.95)'. Accelerate economic growth of district (M= 4.09), Increase in living standard (M= 4.00), Create market for local products (M= 4.29), Creates more employment opportunities (M= 4.46), Helps in removing community backwardness (M= 4.10).

Hypothesis 3 and 4, which proposed a significant relationship between personal and environmental factors and which are as community participation is significantly influenced by personal factor and other

one as community participation is significantly influenced by environmental factor. The results reveal significant SRW values (SRW= 0.756, $p= 0.00$) for the personal factor and (SRW= 0.687, $p=0.00$) for the environmental factor which support the acceptance of these two hypothesis.

Hypothesis 5 to 7, which were framed for the benefits derived by the local inhabitants in the form of economic, social and tourism development. Which were proposed as destination development significantly contributes for economic, social and tourism development. The results found positive relations between the destination building and its outcomes which are depicted by its SRW values.

Destinations building positively contribute towards economic development followed by tourism and social development as depicted by their SRW values which are as (SRW= 0.897, $p= 0.00$) for the economic development (SRW= 0.743, $p= 0.00$) for the social development and (SRW= 0.656, $p= 0.00$) for the tourism development.

The results depict that investment in the physical and infrastructural development has created a lot of benefits for the local community in terms of improvement in the quality of roads and other public facilities. Besides, some respondents have shown more favorable attitude due to the economic benefits attained by them and the people who likely had the most social and cultural ties to the study area favored the social benefits of destination building.

In this research, positive attitude of local inhabitants were connected with the belief that tourism creates more jobs and opportunities for earning income, promotes agricultural markets and most importantly it creates market for the local products which has become a major source of income for many livelihoods.

In terms of positive perception the economic and personal factor were viewed as the most important elements for the local community development as well as for the increasing the national income. Thus, increasing the employability of local residents through destination building helps a lot of families to get out of poverty as well. Meanwhile, the respondents were more concerned about the environmental factor it is because the quality of natural phenomena could deteriorate due to inefficient human activities.

The results delineate that community-based tourism helps the local community in promoting their culture and traditions at larger platform. There are many tourist destinations which are still in depleting conditions due to the negligence by the government sector, so it is recommended that the later should provide credit facilities in order to improve their conditions.

Moreover, the results of this study highlighted the importance of opportunities available for the local

inhabitants as a predictor of community participation in destination building. The findings show an absence of residents in decision making process. So, given suitable opportunities local inhabitants may also be interested in becoming involved in decision making process due because this could lead to more active participation of community members.

Therefore, in order to achieve sustainability the government and local authorities should focus more upon providing suitable opportunities, encourage participation and provide channel to communicate with the community.

5 CONCLUSIONS

This study focused upon the factors influencing local community members in destination development benefits derived out of it by the local inhabitants. To the best of our knowledge, few studies have explored the factors influencing local community in tourism development and its repercussions and that too in the developed nation's only and it becomes very difficult to generalize the finding of these studies, as the culture, needs and perception of the local inhabitants differ across the world.

It can be concluded that residents are willing to support future tourism development dependent upon the economic benefits derived out of it. Therefore, the work contributes to greater theoretical development for the field of travel and tourism. Therefore, this may be somewhat of a landmark study in both the resident perception and community-based tourism literature.

This study also has some valuable practical implications with which to inform the management of domestic tourism and destination developers in the J&K context and especially for the authority of district Poonch. Moreover, District Poonch being a hilly terrain the possibility of agricultural expansion and industrial development is limited due to scarcity of raw material and location on Indo-Pak border.

Community development through tourism is the only feasible approach for the development of district Poonch. Thus, policy makers must accord priority to tourism development in district Poonch. It may be concluded from the comprehensive data analyses, procedures followed and the results reported in this study that for successful destination building, sustainability and management at any destination a more thorough understanding of residents' attitudes and behaviors toward tourism should be made.

Consequently, it is necessary to have a rich pool of studies, having been conducted in different countries, before any inferences can be made. As such, this study makes a valuable contribution to this growing pool of literature.

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